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P. M. B. 1515,
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geostudiesjournal@gmail.com

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Address:	Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
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ASSESSING TRENDS IN AGRICULTURAL EXPANSION, VEGETATION RECOVERY, AND LANDSCAPE STABILISATION IN SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA (1984 -2024)

Abdulumumin Garba Budah¹, Sunday Olukayode Oladejo², Fakpor Akpofure Miller³ and Micheal Ajide Oyinloye⁴

¹Department of Geography, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto

^{2,3,4}Department of Remote Sensing and Geosciences, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Federal University of Technology, Akure

Corresponding Author E-mail: budahabdull@gmail.com,

Abstract: *This study assessed the spatiotemporal dynamics of Land Use and Land Cover Change (LULCC) in Sokoto State, Nigeria, over 40 years (1984–2024), with focus on agricultural expansion and vegetation dynamics. It utilized multi-temporal Landsat satellite imagery and Google Earth Engine for image differencing and trend index analysis. The study revealed four distinct phases of landscape transformation: an initial period (1984–1994) of widespread agricultural expansion, a two-decade phase (1994–2014) of relative landscape stabilization and vegetation recovery, and a recent phase (2014–2024) marked by simultaneous vegetation regeneration and moderate cropland resurgence. According to the LULC categorization indices, farmland was responsible for more than 86% of land transformation in the first ten years, but during the stabilization phase, it decreased to less than 1%, and then increased further to 11.45% in the last ten years. Between 2014 and 2024, the vegetation recovery index reached a peak at 78%, indicating a rise in environmental consciousness and land restoration initiatives. The significance of sustainable land management, ongoing geospatial monitoring, and policy changes to strike a balance between ecological restoration and agricultural development, is highlighted by these patterns, which are consistent with larger regional and global land change trends. The findings provide information for directing land use planning in the study area. It also highlighted the necessity of continuous geospatial monitoring, sustainable land management practices, and more investigation into the socio-ecological causes and effects of LULCC in dry and semi-arid areas such as Sokoto.*

Keywords: Agricultural expansion, vegetation recovery, landscape stabilisation, geospatial monitoring, Sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's topography and vegetation cover have seen considerable alterations, according to recent studies. Over the past 30 years, there has been a linear increase in both agricultural expansion and deforestation, while agricultural employment has stabilized since around 2013 (Olunisi, 2024). Remote Sensing

analysis explains 98% of the variance in vegetation cover, which also indicates both positive and negative trends in vegetation dynamics from 1983 to 2011 (Osunmadewa et al., 2015). Recent studies in Sokoto State, Nigeria, have highlighted significant land-use changes and environmental challenges. Mining activities have led to substantial vegetation loss and increased bare soil, though

some natural regeneration is occurring (Idris Yusuf Ayab et al., 2024). Across northern Nigeria, including Sokoto, extensive loss of vegetation cover has been observed from 1984 to 2016, correlating with rising temperatures and population density (Nwilo et al., 2020a). Despite these trends, rainfall in Sokoto has shown an increasing pattern from 1987 to 2016, with earlier onset dates and later cessation dates, extending the hydrological growing season (Ekoh, 2020). Other studies have shown that there has been a notable increase in urbanization and a decline in vegetation in recent decades. While agricultural and open spaces have declined, built-up areas have grown quickly, doubling roughly every 30 years (Dangulla et al., 2020a). With maximum temperatures rising from 30.6°C in 1986 to 34.6°C in 2016, urbanization has caused land surface temperatures to rise. (Ogunjobi et al., 2018). Between 1984 and 2019, the Sokoto-Rima River Basin's Forest areas shrank by 7.29%, while farmlands and grasslands grew (Usman Abdulrauf Magaji et al., 2022). These developments have a broader impact on northern Nigeria than just Sokoto. Almost 46,000 km² of vegetation were lost in northern states, including the Lake Chad region, between 1984 and 2016, at rates over 2% annually (Ayanlade & Ojebisi, 2019). These land cover changes are closely linked to desertification processes in the region.

From 1984 to 2024, the trends in land use and land cover (LULC) dynamics in Sokoto State, Nigeria, were evaluated in this study, with an emphasis on landscape stabilisation, vegetation recovery, and agricultural growth. The study monitored changes in agriculture and vegetation cover by examining multi-temporal Landsat data. The study aimed to

shed light on the factors influencing these shifts, especially concerning environmental regulations, agricultural demands, and population expansion. Additionally, to mitigate desertification and improve ecological resilience in Sokoto and other semi-arid locations, the study also investigated the possibilities for vegetation regeneration and sustainable land management techniques.

STUDY AREA

Sokoto State, in northwestern Nigeria, lies in the sub-Saharan Sudan belt of West Africa in a zone of savannah-type vegetation (Adegboyega et al., 2016). As part of the Sokoto Basin, the State is located between latitudes 10°30' N and 14°00' N, and longitudes 3°30'E and 7°00'E (Bonde et al., 2014). Figure 1 presents an overview of the study area. According to 'Sokoto' (2024), with a land area of 28,232.37km², Sokoto State is bordered by the Republic of Niger to the north and west for 363km, and the states of Zamfara to the east, Kebbi to the south and west (Figure 1). The state occupies an area of short-grass savanna vegetation in the south and thorn scrub in the north. It is a generally arid region that gradually merges into the desert across the border in Niger (Adegboyega et al., 2016). The foundation of Sokoto's economy and the anchor of its socioeconomic structure is agriculture. Rich riverine floodplains in the area are ideal for growing a wide variety of cash crops, including rice, cotton, and peanuts (groundnuts) (Adams, 1986). The vast farming methods that include the growth of cotton and rice further define the agricultural environment (Last, 2021).

Figure 1: The Study Area
Source: (DIVA GIS 2024)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

TYPES AND SOURCES OF DATA

A comprehensive image of the changing terrain can only be generated by strategically

integrating multi-date data types from numerous sources when investigating the dynamics of land use and land cover. Table 1 offers a description of the data used in this study.

Table 1: Data Description

Dataset	Scale/Resolution(m)	Date of Acquisition	Source
Landsat 3 MSS	60m	1984	USGS
Landsat 5 TM Tier 1 Surface Reflectance	30m	1990	USGS
Landsat 7 ETM+ Tier 1 Surface Reflectance	30m	2000	USGS
Landsat 7 ETM+ Tier 1 Surface Reflectance	30m	2010	USGS
Landsat 8 OLI Tier 1 Surface Reflectance	30m	2024	USGS
Nigeria Shapefiles	N/A	N/A	DIVA GIS
Ground Control Points	N/A	N/A	Field Survey

Source: (Authors Collections 2025)

This study examines changes in land use and land cover (LULC) in Sokoto State, a tropical region with a single rainy season, using historical Landsat data from the United States Geological Survey (USGS). The research improved the accuracy of LULC categorization while evaluating trends in agricultural expansion and vegetation recovery by focusing on the dry season (November to February), when vegetation is sparse. Data processed by Google Earth Engine (GEE) from 1984 to 2024 include pre-

processing methods such as geometric and radiometric corrections for enhanced longitudinal analysis. The Random Forest method ensures reliable classification, while

the FAO's hierarchical LULC classification system provides the foundation for categorizing different types of land. An outline of the processes in the methodology workflow is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Study Workflow
Source: Authors Compilation 2025

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LAND USE AND LAND COVER CHANGE IN THE AREA

Table 1 summarises the changes in Sokoto State's land cover during the four decades (1984–2024) and indicates the areas (in Km²) that either stayed the same, underwent slight changes in dense vegetation, or saw a significant conversion to agricultural land.

Table 1: LULCC in Sokoto State by Category (1984–2024)

Period	No Change	Dense Vegetation (Moderate Change)	Cropland (Significant Change)
1984–1994	313,366.51	127,810.89	2,760,003.40
1994–2004	1,660,015.68	1,456,632.28	84,532.85
2004–2014	2,020,904.58	1,171,926.22	8,350.01
2014–2024	331,082.15	2,593,720.55	378,249.95

Source: (Authors Analysis, 2025)

The image differencing analysis of Land Use and Land Cover Change (LULCC) in Sokoto State from 1984 to 2024 four distinct phases of land transformation as depicted in Figure 3. During the first period (1984–1994), Sokoto

State experienced a significant expansion in cropland, with considerable change recorded over approximately 27,600 km². This indicates a widespread conversion of natural landscapes to agricultural land, likely driven

by population growth, increased demand for food production, and limited land management policies. In contrast, the area of dense vegetation with moderate change was relatively low, at approximately 1,278 km², indicating either degradation of natural vegetation or inadequate afforestation efforts. Only 3,134 km² of land remained unchanged during this decade, indicating that most of the landscape was actively transformed. These results align with recent research on land use and land cover change (LULCC) in Nigeria, which shows significant changes in several areas. For example, in northern Nigeria, including Sokoto State, there is a discernible trend of cropland and built-up area expansion

at the expense of natural vegetation and wetlands (Akinyemi & Ifejika Speranza, 2024; Nwilo et al., 2020b). This pattern is especially noticeable in the Sokoto metropolis, where rapid urban growth is expected to drastically reduce the amount of available farmland and open spaces in the ensuing decades (Dangulla et al., 2020b). Similar dynamics have been noted in neighbouring Kebbi State, where growing farmland and bare/grassland areas are accompanied by a marked decrease in dense vegetation (Aliero et al., 2022). This supports the current findings and further highlights the urgency of implementing sustainable land management strategies and policy interventions to curb ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss.

Figure 3: LULCC 1984 - 1994

Source: (Author’s analysis based on Landsat imagery from the United States Geological Survey USGS, 2025)

The landscape stabilised between 1994 and 2004, with 16,600 km² of land remaining unchanged. As illustrated in Figure 4, it is interesting to note that dense vegetation under moderate change increased significantly throughout this time, reaching 14,566 km², which may indicate a period of reforestation, vegetation regeneration, or less land pressure in some places. The area of cropland drastically decreased to just 845 km² compared to the previous decade, suggesting that agricultural frontiers are not expanding as much. This could be because of policy interventions, land exhaustion, or a move towards more sustainable practices. These findings are consistent with recent research highlighting the accelerating pace of land transformation both in Nigeria and globally. In Nigeria, cropland expanded significantly from 22% to 37% between 2000 and 2022, while tree cover and wetlands declined sharply, from

50% to 31% and from 7% to 3.7%, respectively (Akinyemi & Ifejika Speranza, 2024; Potapov et al., 2021). This mirrors global trends, where cropland areas increased by 9% between 2003 and 2019, with nearly half (49%) of this expansion replacing natural vegetation (Potapov et al., 2021). The results further corroborate historical data showing a drastic reduction in dense vegetation in Nigeria, which declined from 358,534.2 km² in 1981 to 207,812 km² by 2010 (Fashae et al., 2017). This shows a notable shift from past patterns documented between 1994 and 2004, when mild increases in dense vegetation (14,566 km²) coincided with a reduction in cropland to just 845 km² (Asadu et al., 2004). The contrast between these earlier and more recent trends underscores the intensifying tension between agricultural expansion and the preservation of ecological systems, particularly across African landscapes (Akinyemi & Speranza, 2024; Potapov et al., 2021).

Figure 4: LULCC (1994 -2004)

Source: (Author’s analysis based on Landsat imagery from the United States Geological Survey USGS,2025)

The study observed that the stabilization trend continued between 2004 to 2014. The extent of unchanged land further increased to 20,209 km², suggesting a more settled land use system. However, the area of dense vegetation decreased slightly to 11,719 km², possibly due to minor land degradation or the slowing down of previous afforestation efforts. The area under significant cropland change was minimal, at just 84 km², implying that there was little new agricultural development or that existing farmlands were being reused rather than expanded as indicated in Figure 5.

These observations are reinforced by international evaluations that demonstrate complex and regionally varied land use change processes. According to recent studies, about one-third of the Earth's land area changed between 1960 and 2019, four times as

much as was previously thought (Winkler et al., 2021). While earlier studies emphasised the destruction of forests worldwide, newer data shows that, despite continuous losses in tropical forests, tree cover increased by 7.1% between 1982 and 2016, mostly as a result of afforestation in extratropical areas (Reardon et al., 1999; Song et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018). This study, like other studies in Sub-Saharan Africa, which has experienced a fast and broad conversion of forests to farmland, with notable national and subnational variations (Braithwaite & Vlek, 2004). This continental trend is consistent with the current findings, which indicate that farmland expansion and natural vegetation loss are accelerating throughout Nigeria, especially in the northwest. A distinct trajectory is shown by land use transitions in places like China, which are marked by a steady total area of agriculture but greater fragmentation as a result of urbanisation (Yu et al., 2018).

Figure 5: LULCC 2004 - 2014

Source: (Author's analysis based on Landsat imagery from the United States Geological Survey, USGS, 2025).

The study revealed once again, changes in trend between 2014 and 2024, indicating a strong phase of vegetation recovery or regeneration. The area of dense vegetation under moderate modification increased dramatically to a record 25,937 km². Increased environmental consciousness, climate action initiatives, or modifications in land use practices may be the cause of this. Concurrently, cropland expansion saw a mild rebound, with 3,783 km² undergoing notable change, indicating a revitalized agricultural activity that may have been fueled by improved agricultural support systems or population growth. It is interesting to note that the volume of unaltered land decreased dramatically to 3,311 km², indicating a renewed dynamism in land use that may have

resulted from urbanization, agricultural resurgence, or reforestation.

The trends in vegetation recovery and changes in land use are mostly supported by recent studies. Farmland abandonment and conservation measures in Northern China led to a significant recovery of forests and shrub land in mountainous areas (Wang et al., 2016). This is consistent with the minor recovery in farmland expansion that has been documented. The trend of vegetation recovery was supported by afforestation initiatives in Xinjiang, China, which had a 4% increase in wooded area between 2000 and 2022 (Shobairi et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2016). However, natural vegetation was displaced by half of new cropland worldwide, suggesting possible conflicts with the objectives of ecosystem protection (Potapov et al., 2021).

Figure 6: LULCC 2014 - 2024

Source: (Author’s analysis based on Landsat imagery from the United States Geological Survey USGS,2025).

TRENDS IN LAND STABILITY (NO CHANGE), VEGETATION RECOVERY, AND CROPLAND EXPANSION

Table 2: Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) Classification Index

Period	No Change Index (%)	Vegetation Change Index (%)	Cropland Change Index (%)
1984–1994	9.78909126282402	3.992617036813416	86.21829170036257
1994–2004	51.85635484301182	45.50296801260657	2.6406771443816073
2004–2014	63.12997296769377	36.60918547115744	0.26084156114880624
2014–2024	10.023520212431372	78.5249532731487	11.451526514419927

Source: (Authors Analysis, 2025)

A trend analysis of land changes in Sokoto State over four decades, from 1984 to 2024, is presented in the Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) Classification Index Table (Table 2). The study revealed notable changes in land use patterns, ranging from aggressive agricultural expansion to periods of landscape stabilization and, more recently, extensive vegetation recovery. Sokoto State's agricultural land expanded rapidly over the first ten years (1984–1994), as seen by the cropland change index, which peaked at 86.22%. This implies that the bulk of the land was turned into farming, most likely as a result of rising food consumption and population increase. However, at 3.99%, the vegetation change index was noticeably low, suggesting that nothing was being done to promote natural regeneration or afforestation. The fact that only 9.79% of the land was unaltered suggests that the landscape underwent significant change over this time.

However, the period from 1994 to 2004 was marked by significant stabilization and ecological recovery, with more than half of the land (51.86%) remaining unchanged. The vegetation change index rose sharply to 45.50%, indicating a combination of reduced land pressure, potential policy interventions, or natural regrowth processes. Additionally, cropland expansion dropped sharply to just 2.64%, signaling a departure from the

intensive agricultural activities of the previous decade. The tendency of stabilization persisted between 2004 and 2014, when the no change index peaked at 63.13%. Despite a slight decline to 36.61%, the vegetation change index remained a reliable measure of ongoing vegetation regeneration. With just 0.26%, cropland expansion was virtually nonexistent during this period, likely due to more effective land use techniques or agricultural practices.

The most recent decade (2014–2024) demonstrated a renewed dynamism in land use: the vegetation change index increased to 78.52%, indicating a strong period of afforestation, environmental restoration, or shifting land use behaviors that may have been influenced by climate initiatives; cropland expansion experienced a moderate resurgence at 11.45%, which could be ascribed to renewed population pressures or improved agricultural support systems; and the no change index fell precipitously to 10.02%, indicating significant changes in land cover, most likely due to urbanization, land recovery, or intensified farming. From the foregoing, the LULC indices show how the landscape of Sokoto changed from extensive land conversion in the 1980s to growing vegetation recovery and land stability in the following decades.

Figure 7 LULCC Trend (1984 – 2024)

Source: (Author’s analysis based on Landsat imagery from the United States Geological Survey (USGS,2025).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A study of Land Use and Land Cover Change (LULCC) in Sokoto State between 1984 and 2024 revealed that different forces, such as human activities and environmental factors, have influenced how the landscape changed. The key findings of image differencing analysis include: early years with steep land conversion and little vegetation growth, then a time of landscape stabilization and vegetation progress, a deceleration in cropland change, and more recent increases in both vegetation growth and cropland. This pattern is further supported by using LULC classification indices for trend analysis. A huge amount of agricultural land was changed between 1984 and 1994, exploring how crops play a major part in land change. Between 1994 and 2014, stability rose, and there was a significant shift toward nature recovery as the vegetation change index increased and cropland

development fell to under 1%. Nevertheless, in the last ten years (2014–2024), land dynamism increased, with the vegetation change index going higher than 78% and cropland expansion beginning to grow again, becoming 11.45%.

The observed changes are linked to notable trends globally, with Sub-Saharan Africa dealing with increasing land use as humans strive for sustainability. Sokoto State’s experience confirms that better land information, unified land planning, and sustainable agricultural practices are required. This indicates that constant remote monitoring of land use and land cover is important for monitoring and steering adaptive management. Although recent decades have witnessed improvement in environmental and land management in Sokoto, these gains are still in danger due to a fast-rising population, more urban areas, and the need for more farmland.

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